

High-Speed Issues Mitigation of GaN Power Transistors Based on a New Gate Driving Profile

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Abstract—This paper presents a new gate-driving profile to mitigate the switching issues caused by high-speed operation of GaN transistors in on-off transitions. The concept consists of modifying the primary PWM signal applied to the GaN transistors to an appropriate voltage profile, which changes the gate-source voltage behaviour in the critical stage of the GaN transitions. The gate-driving concept is evaluated on LTspice, and the results show the reduction of ringing and overshoots when applying the proposal while maintaining tolerable power losses.

Index Terms—GaN, gate driving, LTspice, wide bandgap devices.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wide bandgap (WBG) devices, such as silicon carbide (SiC) and Gallium-Nitride (GaN) transistors, are expected to meet the new power converter requirements. Their improvements in intrinsic characteristics concerning high-speed operation, high voltages, current processing, and low power dissipation allow them to achieve high efficiency and high-power density converters [1]–[3]. Compared to SiC MOSFETs, GaN transistors can operate at higher speed with lower on-state resistance $R_{DS,ON}$, leading to low switching losses and enabling high-efficiency power converters [4]–[6]. Nevertheless, high-speed operation of the GaN transistor causes ringing and overshoots in the voltages and currents, which can induce electromagnetic interference (EMI) [7], [8]. Therefore, high switching speed requires more attention to circuit design to significantly reduce parasitic elements.

Optimizing PCB layout is crucial to reduce parasitic elements and their effects. The authors have presented methods for designing PCB layouts to reduce parasitic inductances [5], [9], [10], mainly the gate loop parasitic inductance and the power loop parasitic inductance (L_{loop}), which are critical for high-speed operation of the GaN [8], [10], [11]. However, even if the inductance can be reduced, oscillations occur at higher voltages and frequencies. Conventional gate drivers based on pull-up or pull-on resistors or two diodes and two resistances to control the turn-on and turn-off transition of the GaN can improve the switching of devices [8]. However, high-speed problems are not completely avoided.

Gate driving techniques and circuits can improve the behaviour of GaN devices. In the literature, some gate driver concepts and ICs drivers presented for SiC MOSFETs could

be adapted and used for GaN devices [12]–[14]. However, particular features of the GaN transistors, such as lower gate voltage and higher speed operation, limit the gate driver systems available for SiC devices.

Gate driver methods and circuits for GaN transistors have also been investigated and evaluated [15]. Reported driving techniques include two-step [16], three-step [17], or multi-stage approaches [18]–[21], which create gate voltage or current waveform profiles to control the turn-on and turn-off slopes and mitigate the high-speed GaN issues. Multi-stage gate drivers use low-power switches governed by a digital controller to change the gate resistance or voltage supplies to achieve different voltage or current profiles or patterns at the gate of the transistor. Many multi-stage gate drivers were developed as monolithic systems integrated into a chip [22], [23]. The effects of stray inductance and circuit noise are reduced with monolithic drivers, and complex arrays of gate transistors can be combined to achieve high-level structures. However, monolithic solutions are limited to specific applications and known loads, and the gate driver architecture cannot change once integrated.

Gate driving methods and circuits presented in the state-of-the-art have advantages and disadvantages. Generally speaking, the solutions can reduce overshoots and oscillations with acceptable transition performance. However, many gate drivers are complex and limited to specific applications and low-voltage and power systems. Consequently, new gate-driving solutions need to be investigated to improve GaN transitions, especially for high-power applications.

This manuscript presents a new gate-driving concept that modifies the PWM signal to transform it into a custom profile to change the gate-source voltage behaviour in the on-off transition. Thus, it reduces overshoots and oscillations and keeps switching power losses low. This manuscript contributes a new concept of gate driving that can reduce overshoots and oscillations and maintain the high-frequency switching performance of the GaN transistors. The gate-driving concept is evaluated by LTspice simulations, which confirm the reduction of high-speed problems of GaN devices.

The rest of the manuscript is organised as follows: Section II presents the gate-driving concept and operation principle. Section III shows the definitions of the main gate drive parameters. Meanwhile, section IV evaluates gate driving using

LTspice simulations. Finally, Section V concludes this work.

II. GATE DRIVER CONCEPT AND OPERATING PRINCIPLE

The gate driving approach consists of creating a custom gate voltage (V_g) profile to control the power applied on the different transition stages of the GaN transistor at the turn-on and turn-off trajectories, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. GaN power transistor waveforms and gate voltage expected profile.

Considering Fig. 2 and with respect to Fig. 1, in the first half of the PWM period, the V_g profile starts just as the conventional PWM for regular charging the input capacitances up to the Miller plateau at t_2 . At this point, V_g falls to Miller Voltage (V_{Miller}) to limit the gate current (I_g); from this point, the V_g goes increasing until the gate-source voltage (V_{gs}) reaches the nominal V_{cc} , at t_4 , using a slope as reference. From this time, V_g remains at V_{cc} until the first half of the PWM period ends.

It is important to note that the V_{Miller} of the V_{gs} with standard PMM (red waveform) defines the inflexion point for shaping the V_g profile. When the V_g profile is applied, the new V_{gs} (dotted waveform in Fig. 1) will cause a lower level of V_{Miller} due to the drop voltage of R_g . As the V_{Miller} with new V_{gs} is lower than conventional V_{gs} , the gate driving would warranty the expected results.

Considering Fig. 1, in the second half of the PWM period, the V_g profile remains just as the conventional PWM for regular discharging of the output capacitances until the Miller plateau ends, (t_8). At this point, V_g rises to V_{Miller} to restrict the I_g ; from this point, the V_g goes until the V_{gs} reaches the nominal lower voltage (GND) using a slope as a reference. From this time, V_g remains at GND until the second half of the PWM period ends.

With the defined V_g profile, the drain current (I_d) and drain-source voltage (V_{ds}) should behave better, with lower oscillations in both turn-on and turn-off transitions.

However, in high-power applications, it is essential to consider a number of factors with great care.

Fig. 2. Equivalent model circuit to evaluate the GaN devices and gate-driving concept.

Firstly, it is of paramount importance to optimize component locations and minimize track distances by using short traces, thus reducing parasitic inductances present on the printed circuit board (PCB). Secondly, it is necessary to minimize copper region areas and use low-inductance materials. Thirdly, the inductance of the power bus cable can also affect and significantly increase overshoot and oscillations.

Another crucial aspect is the selection of an appropriate power supply for the GaN power transistor gate driver. The driver must be capable of providing the necessary current and voltage to facilitate a rapid and efficient switching process.

III. GATE DRIVING PARAMETER DEFINITION

As shown in Fig. 1, the V_{Miller} and transition stages are essential for the gate-driving definition. Therefore, these parameters must be known or calculated to achieve the expected results.

A. Miller voltage definition

The V_{Miller} could be calculated by (1) by means threshold voltage (V_{th}) and transconductance (g_m).

$$V_{Miller} = V_{th} + \frac{I_L}{g_m} \Rightarrow g_m = \frac{I_L}{V_{Miller} - V_{th}} \quad (1)$$

Manufacturers always provide the V_{th} , and often, they proportionate the V_{Miller} as constant and same value for turn-on and turn-off. In practice, V_{Miller} can change due to system dynamic and could be different for turn-on and turn-off transitions. Nevertheless, V_{Miller} has been defined in the literature [24] and can be approximated by (3) and (4).

$$V_{Miller-on} = \left(\frac{V_{th}g_mR_gC_{GD} + I_LR_gC_{GD} + V_g(C_{GD} + C_{DS})}{(1 + g_mR_g)C_{GD} + C_{DS}} \right) \quad (2)$$

and consequently,

$$V_{Miller-off} = \left(\frac{V_{th}g_mR_gC_{GD} + I_LR_gC_{GD}}{(1 + g_mR_g)C_{GD} + C_{DS}} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where the capacitances CGD and CDS can be obtained by $C_{iss} = C_{gs} + C_{gd}$, $C_{oss} = C_{ds} + C_{gd}$, and $C_{rss} = C_{gd}$. The capacitances C_{iss} , C_{oss} , C_{rss} can be found in the datasheets by the manufacturer.

It is crucial to note that, for the purpose of evaluating the proposed concept, the parameters are fixed in order to facilitate the conduct of the tests and a comparison to determine if there are improvements.

B. Definition of time stages

With respect to Fig. 1, the time stages of the turn-on and turn-off trajectories can be defined as follows:

1) Turn-on:

- $t_{don} = t_0 + t_1$. Turn-on delay time is the time it takes for the V_{gs} to go from the lowest voltage (0 V) to V_{th} , from when it is activated until it begins to rise I_d .
- $t_{ir} = t_1 + t_2$. Drain current rise time is the time it takes for the drain current to reach its maximum value (I_d) from 0 A, and it may vary depending on the load and the value of V_g .
- $t_{vf} = t_2 + t_3$. Drain-source voltage fall time is the time it takes for V_{ds} to fall from nominal to lowest voltage (0 V).

2) Turn-off:

- $t_{doff} = t_6 + t_7$. Turn-off delay time is the time it takes for V_{gs} to change from nominal voltage to V_{Miller} , which is the time in which it begins to rise V_{ds} .
- $t_{vr} = t_7 + t_8$. Voltage rise time is the time it takes for V_{gs} to remain at V_{Miller} ; it is also the time it takes for V_{ds} to rise from low to nominal voltage.
- $t_{if} = t_8 + t_9$. During the current fall time, once V_{ds} reaches nominal voltage, I_d begins to decrease, and V_{gs} changes from V_{Miller} to V_{th} . This interval ends when V_{gs} reaches V_{th} , and I_d goes 0 A

There are various methods to obtain these times. The manufacturer provides approximate times for these sections; however, they are defined as an ideal case study without considering circuits parasitic elements. This simple model differs from the final application, where various parasitic elements are present, such as the transistor loop inductances, power loop inductances and the printed circuit parasitic elements. In the literature, models often fit equations and models to determine the energy and losses of transistors, seeking values closer to real behavior [24]–[27]. Table I shows the proposed equations to approximate the time stages.

IV. GATE-DRIVER EVALUATION BY MEAN LTSPICE SIMULATIONS

The gate-driving concept is validated by simulation in LTspice using the circuit shown in Fig. 3, based on the circuit defined in Fig. 2. The GaN transistor model GS66516T by GaN System was used for all validations in this manuscript. In addition, the parameters for the gate driving evaluation are shown in Table II.

TABLE I
EQUATION FOR CALCULATING TIMES STAGES

Stage	Times by calculations
t_{don}	$t_{d-on} = (R_g C_{iss}) \ln \left(\frac{V_{gs}}{(V_{gs} - V_{Miller}) - V_{TH}} \right)$
t_{ir}	$t_{ir} = \left(5 * (R_g (C_{gd1} + C_{gs})) \right) - t_{don}$
t_{vf}	$t_{vf} = R_g * \left(\frac{Q_{gd}}{V_{DS}} \right) * \left(\frac{V_{DS}}{V_{gs} - V_{miller}} \right)$
t_{end-on}	$t_{\tau 2} = 5 * (R_g (C_{gd2} + C_{gs}))$
$t_{on-total}$	$T_{on_total} = t_{d-on} + t_{ir} + t_{vf} + \tau_2$
t_{doff}	$t_{d-off} = \tau_2 = 5 * (R_g (C_{gd2} + C_{gs}))$
t_{vr}	$t_{vr} = R_g * \left(\frac{Q_{gd}}{V_{DS}} \right) * \left(\frac{V_{DS}}{V_{Miller-off}} \right)$
t_{if}	$t_{if} = \sqrt{(g_m * I_d) * (R_g * C_{gd}) * \left(\frac{V_{Miller} - V_{th}}{V_{Miller}} \right)}$
$t_{end-off}$	$t_{\tau 1} = R_g C_{iss} \ln \left(\frac{V_{th}}{0.01 * V_{th}} \right)$
$t_{off-total}$	$T_{off_total} = t_{d-off} + t_{vr} + t_{if} + t_{\tau}$

Fig. 3. LTspice model for gate driving evaluation.

A. Time stage evaluation

A time stage calculation was performed to approximate the time stages necessary for the gate driving approach considering Fig. 1, which are t_2 , t_4 , t_8 , and t_{10} . Time stages were calculated using Table I and the specifications shown in Table II. On the other hand, simulations were developed to measure the times. Table III compares the equivalent time stages obtained by analytics and simulations.

Regarding the results, the time steps have the same order of magnitude, with partial errors in the main measurements that define the new PWM pulse shape of 36 % in the case of $(t_{don} + t_{ir})$ and 12.5 % for time $(t_{vf} + (t_3 - t_4))$. This confirming that the equations used in Table II can be used to define the times required for the gate driving proposed.

TABLE II
PARAMETERS FOR GATE-DRIVING EVALUATION

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
V_{DC}	200 V	L_d	5 nH
Load Current	18 A	L_g	5 nH
F_s	100 kHz	L_s	10 nH
Duty	50 %	L_{loop}	100 nH
T_s	10 us	L_{load}	470 uH
C_{ds}	120.1 pF	R_{load}	20 Ω
C_{gd}	5.9 pF	R_g	10 Ω
C_{gs}	512.1 pF	V_{gs}	6 V
C_{iss}	518 pF	V_{Miller}	3 V
C_{oss}	126 pF	V_{th}	1.7 V
C_{rss}	5.9 pF	$V_{Miller-on}$	2 V
Q_{GD}	5.4 nC	$V_{Miller-off}$	1 V

TABLE III
TRANSITION TIMES COMPARISON BY CALCULATIONS AND SIMULATIONS

Stage	Times by calculations	Times by simulations
$t_2 = t_{don} + t_{ir}$	25.86 ns	15.42 ns
$t_4 = t_2 + t_{vf} + t_{end-on}$	74.49 ns	58.64 ns
$t_8 = t_{doff} + t_{vr}$	66.6 ns	52.54 ns
$t_{10} = t_8 + t_{if} + t_{end-off}$	123.25 ns	97.23 ns

B. Gate-driving Evaluation

The expected profile was programmed in LTspice, and the gate driving concept was evaluated based on the conditions defined in Table II and the times obtained in Table III. In addition, to analyze the performance advantages, the gate driving was compared with conventional gate driving based on a single R_g . The behaviour of the V_{gs} and V_{ds} voltage and drain current waveforms is shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Meanwhile, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show an enlarged V_{ds} and I_d peaks comparison.

Fig. 4. Turn-on waveform comparison between GaN under standard PWM and proposed gate driving. $R_g = 10 \Omega$ and $V_{Miller} = 2$ V, $t_2 = 25$ ns, $t_4 = 80$ ns.

Fig. 5. Enlargement of V_{ds} and I_d waveform comparison between GaN under standard PWM and proposed gate driving to turn-on.

Regarding the results, the oscillations and current peak on I_{ds} are reduced and the delay times are the same for V_{gs} and I_{ds} , meanwhile, for V_{ds} , the delay time is affected slightly.

Fig. 6. Turn-off waveform comparison between GaN under standard PWM and proposed gate driving. $R_g = 10 \Omega$ and $V_{Miller} = 1$ V, $t_8 = 66$ ns, $t_{10} = 150$ ns.

Like turn-on, the oscillations tend to decrease for turn-off, and the delay time only manifests on the I_d current. To verify the performance, a quantitative comparison of the GaN power losses between the gate-driving approach and conventional gate driver was performed. Table III shows the power losses obtained using LTspice software.

The comparison shows that the proposed gate drive technique has slightly higher switching losses than the conventional method. Regarding the total losses of the device, this increase is 33 %. However, the reduction of peak current I_d and voltage V_{ds} is 40.10 % and 41.10 %, respectively, which reduces the risk of stress and breakage due to overcurrent and overvoltage of the circuit in high-power industrial applications.

Fig. 7. Enlargement of V_{ds} and I_d waveform comparison between GaN under standard PWM and proposed gate driving to turn-off.

TABLE IV
POWER LOSSES COMPARISON BETWEEN GAN UNDER CONVENTIONAL GATE DRIVER AND GATE-DRIVING APPROACH.

	P_{total} (W)	P_{sw-on} (W)	P_{sw-off} (W)	P_{cond} (W)
Conventional	4.2195	2.4612	1.4758	0.3493
Proposed	5.6594	3.1308	2.2859	0.3121

In the case study, when the I_d is relatively low, the device experiences total losses of 33 %. However, it is known that as the current increases to the nominal value, the conduction losses will also increase. In addition, at high power, the switching losses and conduction losses are commonly similar. Therefore, the power loss percentage decreases by approximating the switching and conduction loss values in conventional and modified methods. For instance, if we consider $P_{conduction} = 4W$, conventional losses = $4.2195W + 4W = 8.2W$. Proposed losses are calculated as $5.6594W + 4W + 9.65W$. Based on this calculation, the estimated losses are 17 %, indicating the reliability of this method.

Concerning the show results, it is essential to note that the gate driving concept can be improved and optimized to enhance the results. On the other hand, the authors are working to develop the appropriate circuitry and controller for generating the gate-driving profile approach and develop experimental validations. The fundamental idea of this manuscript was to show a new concept and the opportunity to create alternative solutions for reducing the high-speed issues in the GaN transistors.

TABLE V
THE PERCENTAGE REDUCTION RATIO OF I_d AND V_{ds} WAVEFORM OVERSHOOT

	Turn-on(%)	Turn-off(%)
V_{ds}	42.1	40.1
I_d	46.2	34.0

V. CONCLUSIONS

A gate-driving profile approach was presented and evaluated in this manuscript. This approach is based on a gate driving gate voltage profile, which changes the GaN transistor's behaviour at turn-on and turn-off transitions. The simulations showed that the gate-driving approach can reduce the power current and voltage overshoots and oscillations without considerably increasing the switching losses. These simulations have been the main tool to evaluate the behavior of the GaN power transistor.

The implementation of the gate driver concept requires the consideration of different factors, and the limitations of the components required for the circuitry used in the experimental phase of this work, made it necessary to focus on the verification of the gate driver concept through simulations, with fixed parameters and similar those of the real system.

It is important to note that the simulations have certain limitations, as they cannot fully reproduce real laboratory conditions. Factors such as PCB parasitic inductances, noise and temperature variations can affect the behavior of the GaN power transistor in ways that are not predictable by simulations. In addition, due to the high operating speeds of the proposed gate driver profile, the proposed gate driver has some limitations in terms of component selection.

Although these limitations, experimental investigations are currently underway and will be reported in future publications. Future works for the presented gate driving is related to the development of the profile by using suitable digital or analog hardware, besides validating the gate driving technique through experimental tests.

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